

Trend of Policies on Agriculture to Ensure Food Security in Nigeria

Ayuba Abubakar Fusami¹, Bashir Adamu Gambo², Chikyama Samuel³

¹ Abubakakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi

² Adamawa state Polytechnic Yola

³ Local Government Service Commission Yola, Nigeria

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Abstract: Food security disruption measures has to do with critical food supply to avoid various risk factors over coming period of time and to have significant, yet certain impacts on food security. Adaptation of strategies and policy responses to global food supply chain, change agricultural practices are urgently needed to aid in solving food security problem. For instance lack of sustainable policies on food security issue, budgetary allocation to agricultural sector, Population growth, land use change, environmental factors, currently COVID-19, economic instability, wars, high import and export dependence ratios are making many countries vulnerable to food insecurity. Several approaches are possible for achieving sustainability of food security to ensure sufficient food supply. Majority of the programmes cease to exist and some are no more. The bedeviling issue is to ensure all the initiated programme have reach its targeted goal and should be sustained until the target goal and time is reached. Subsequently a follow up should be executed to assess the level of it success. Government needs to look at the Maputo declaration of committing 10 percent budgetary resources to agriculture ensuring its sustainability then we can dream of sustainable food security.

Keywords: Food, Security and Agriculture.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the FAO, in its definition established at the World Food Summit (WFS), Rome in 1996, food security is achieved when everyone has physical, social and economic access at all times to sufficient, safe and nutritious food to meet their dietary needs, food preferences for an active and healthy life (Cadoni et al. 2013). The factors in the definition have considered: availability, access, utilization and stability. Availability means having sufficient quantities of appropriate food, access means having adequate income or other resources to access food, and utilization/consumption means having adequate dietary intake, the ability to absorb, use nutrients in the body and finally stability means constant flow of the food. The food security in household level refers to the availability of food in one's home which he has access to food, or when the members of the same do not live in hunger or fear of starvation.

The objective this study is to establish an operational concept primarily on food supply problems for availability and to some degree of its stability. The issues of famine, hunger and food crisis were extensively examined, following the events of the mid 1970s with an outcome redefinition food security as recognized behavior of potentially vulnerable to food sufficiency crises. The global concerns of 1974, is the volume and stability of food supplies as the major concerned. The 1994 UNDP Human Development Report promoted the construct of human security, to reflect cross-sectional patterns and trends in food production, supply and consumption chain. However, these variables are different amongst countries and changes with agricultural reliability of food production in a country. It averages food demand-supply chain derived from national aggregates or a national survey estimate as a result of more rapid agricultural development in the States. Enough

food to feed everyone by ensuring availability and access to successfully limits the impact of security risk in cases of natural disaster, an economic shock or a humanitarian problem resulting into a severe food crisis. Sharp reductions in agricultural population, those that produce it or purchasers can have long term effect on policy development which will take years to recover. Natural disasters and conflict have both severe short-term and persisting long-term negative effects in food security of a nation. The 1996 World Summit on Food Security declared that "food should not be used as an instrument for political and economic pressure". Since multiple different international agreements and mechanisms have been developed to address food security. Sustainable Development Goals in particular Goal 2 state that: Zero Hunger should be sets globally and agreed on targets to end hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture by 2030.

However, current crisis in Northern Nigeria (Insurgency, Kidnapping, and Banditry) are ravaging the agricultural potency, there by having a gross effect on the populace. There are significant differences between food security and the factors that are changing rapidly making people becoming vulnerable, fragile to food security in Nigeria's economy. Many reasons can be responsible to increase or decrease in food insecurity, to mention among others: the 2008-9 financial crisis, lack of sustainable policies on food security issue, budgetary allocation to agricultural sector, Population growth, desert encroachment, land use change, land degradation, Flood, pests, diseases currently COVID, high import and export dependence ratios are making many countries vulnerable to food insecurity. Nearly a tenth of the world population still lives on 1.90 USD or less a day, with sub-Saharan Africa and southern Asia the region's most affected. In many low-income economies, like Nigeria, debt has swollen to levels far exceeding its GDP, eroding growth prospects, insurgency and violence, mass displacement people in to IDPs has displaced many families whom are famers: host for agriculture in developing countries. Food security becomes a priority to Nigeria because it dependent on agricultural lifestyle and 80 to 90 percent of all families in rural centres rely upon producing their own food. To discuss some of the factors;

2. FACTOR RESPONSIBLE FOR FOOD INSECURITY IN NIGERIA

2.1 COVID 19

Reduced incomes, disruption of food supply chains, lock down measures, boarder closure, travel ban, ship and cargo movement restriction, inter and intra city movement restrictions have greatly impacted on food production-supply chain and still its negative consequence is yet to be over. It have led to increases in global food insecurity, affecting vulnerable households in almost every country, with impacts expected to continue through 2023, and possibly beyond as the Delta variant continues its spread. COVID-19 has come along with so many policies and measures to curtail its spread. This limits the production-supply chain of agricultural produce, farming activities, trades and etc. The impact of this menace has brought Agricultural Commodity Price Index remain near its highest level as of July 16, 2021 in Nigeria, approximately 30% higher than in January 2020. For example, Maize, wheat, and rice prices were about 43%, 12% and 10% above their January 2020 levels. Surging prices reflect strong demand-related supply disruptions, even though the global production outlook for major grains remains good. The primary risks to food security are higher retail prices, combined with reduced incomes, meaning more households having to cut down on the quantity and quality of their food consumption. Countries are experiencing currency devaluations and high food price inflation at the retail level, this reflects on the lingering supply disruptions chain, since they spend a larger share of their income on food than people in high-income countries. The pandemic is estimated to have dramatically increased the number of people facing acute food insecurity in 2020-2021. According to world food programme (WFP), around 272 million people are already or are at risk of becoming acutely food-insecure in the countries where it operates (Tim Benton, 2016). It however stated that hunger was trending upward even before the COVID-19 pandemic, which exacerbated existing.

2.2 ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

Changing climate and environmental factors have significant yet uncertain impacts on global food security. These may ranges from effects on agriculture such as droughts, increase in climate, changing productivity and livelihood patterns, economic losses, and effects on infrastructure. Food security in future will be linked to our ability to adapt agricultural systems that accommodates extreme events hence risk of a diminished food supply. Approximately 2.4 billion people live in the drainage basin of the rivers. History shows localities that experience flood is followed by severe droughts after the occurrence of the event. In Nigeria alone, the Niger and Benue basin provides water for drinking and farming for more than 20 million people, Chad basin provide same to more than 10 million people, as well river Jamare-Yobe basin and etc. Developing nations have to devise systematic agricultural system to effectively utilize the amount of land available for

best agricultural output. There are several reports of flood activities in Nigeria along these aforesaid rivers. Some of the environmental factors considered here are:

2.3 DRYING OF LAKE CHAD AND ARMED CONFLICTS

The drying of Lake Chad and regional armed conflicts has affected farming population in the Sudano-Sahelian drylands of Nigeria. This region has been so important in fishing and irrigational farming and has been the fore-front in onion production. Not at all, this lake provides water for cattle, sheep and goat rearing population in conjunction with river Jamare-Kumadugu Ghana. This lake has not been dredge for many years and siltation and sedimentation is reducing the capacity and volume of water in the said region. Recently, (in 2022) 43 rice farmers and many more were killed in Borno, Sokkoto, Zamfara and etc states by insurgents. The activities of these insurgent have displaced almost all the farming population in these areas into IDPs camps. This undoubtedly has a knock-on effect on food production-supply chain and can potentially deter farmers output from those regions.

2.4 LAND USE CHANGE

According to Bluebird, China needs not less than 120 million hectares of arable land for its food security. China has reported a surplus of 15 million hectares. It further stated that, by contrast, nearly 4 million hectares of land have been converted in to urban use while 3 million hectares of land have also been contaminated. A survey by Bluebird found that 2.5% of China's arable land is too contaminated to grow food without harm. Similarly in Nigeria, vast arable land where converted for human comfort in most of its urban centers such as road, shelter, arena, schools, etc. these has a great impact on the total arable land which there use where converted to other purposes. Even though, we are yet to run short of land for agricultural activities but the statistics of rate of urbanization is very alarming in most state and local government urban towns. There should be need to have a planned policy towards sustainable land use policy and development control, this will mitigate and regulate land use change and conversion making its management sustainable towards agricultural activities as well to ensure food security sustainability.

2.5 IMPROVING AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY TO BENEFIT THE RURAL POOR

There are strong, direct relationships between agricultural productivity, hunger, poverty, and sustainability (Adbis Ababa, 2014). Three-quarters of the world's poor live in rural areas and make their living from agriculture. Adbis Ababa (2014) says that, the higher the proportion of the rural population that obtains its income solely from subsistence farming the higher the incidence of malnutrition. Fandom also reported that improvements in agricultural productivity aimed at small-scale farmers will benefit the rural poor first in Nigeria. To them, food crop demand is likely to double in the next 50 years, as the global population approaches a projected estimated figure of nine billion. Growing sufficient food will require people to make changes in agriculture productivity for areas reliant on agricultural activities; improving land use management; expanding crop arable land areas; investing improve irrigation system; and reducing gross food demand by influencing diets and reducing post-harvest losses.

International Water Management Institute (IWMI) said that managing rainwater effectively can be good in supplementing small-scale irrigation, this can be very helpful to greater number of poor people. It has called for a new era of water investments and policies for upgrading rain-fed agriculture that would go beyond controlling field-level soil through better local management of rainfall and runoff. Increased agricultural productivity enables farmers to grow more food, which translates into better diets and, under market conditions that offer a level playing field, into higher farm incomes. It may be helpful alliance between the emergency food program and community-supported agriculture. It can be beneficial in some places where food is less processed and grown locally. By IWMI, in tropical countries, adopting a system where by wild food plants can be gathered as alternative method of subsistence and can play an important role in poverty alleviation.

2.6 BUDGETARY ALLOCATION TO AGRICULTURAL SECTOR

The Agricultural sector accounts for 24.43% of all economic activity in Nigeria with almost 90% engagement by locals. Food Production takes up 87.73% of activities in the Agriculture sector. A study on Nigerian budget by Oxfam in 2019 shows the potentiality of this sector is undeniably massive compared with others. Nigeria has over 82 million hectares of arable land area with high agricultural productivity. Nigeria is the largest rice producing country in West Africa according to Folahan (2017) and Cadoni et al., (2013). In addition, the country grows about 50% of grain crops produced in West

Africa. Nigeria is the 3rd largest millet producing country in the world after India and China (Tim, 2016). In 2015, agriculture employed 38% of the working population and generated 23.1% of the GDP (Taiwo 2022). With this, Nigeria is very important in agricultural sector with higher chance in providing food security to the nation’s economy, employment opportunities generation, capacity in economic growth and diversification (Oxfam, 2019).

Studies by Oxfam also show that there is a relationship between government expenditure and economic growth. Some of these studies have looked specifically at the link between government spending and agricultural growth and poverty reduction (Lawrence, 2007). The growths in agriculture and poverty reductions are directly proportional to the effects of public spending in agricultural sectors. Yet, in most developing countries, aid and public expenditure to agriculture is stagnant or on declining (Oxfam, 2019). Hence if African countries wants growth in their economy, government at national and sub-national level have to spend more on agriculture so that there will continued stable driver to its GDP, considering its effect on the sector (Oxfam, 2019). But most atimes, GDP growth do not actually tally with their spending. Looking at Nigeria’s annual budgetary allocation on agricultural sector can glimpse one to determination of the policy towards sustainable food security.

OXFAM Nigeria, reported that, due to Nigeria's crude, farming practice, productivity is low and far in-between. Most of the initiatives in the states are Federal Government initiatives or donor funded projects, these require a commitment of counterpart funds from the states (Oxfam, 2019). One major challenge is that most of the states do not have clear policy directions for agricultural development in their states (Oxfam, 2019). The study further shows that, in nearly all the states that their study covered, agricultural investment is remarkably low, and falls short of the 10 percent Maputo declaration recommendation which has been adopted by many African nations, with most states averaging between 1-3 percent commitment on their budgetary allocation to agricultural sector. Kebbi is the only State where agricultural expenditure as a percentage of the total budget is higher in 2019 than 2014 (Oxfam, 2019). Several state governments have also deployed funding strategies that unlock growth in the agricultural products of their comparative advantage (Taiwo, 2022). It is worth noting that in Katsina and Taraba, share of spending to agriculture is projected to rise by 2019-2021 (to 8.2 percent and 9.6 percent respectively), but much of this increase is driven by ambitious, perhaps unrealistic revenue projections and reliance on donor financing that may materialize or not, in fact largely due to the inability of the state to match the required counterpart funding required by such donor agencies (Oxfam, 2019).

At the Second Ordinary Assembly of the African Union in July 2003 in Maputo, African Heads of State and Government endorsed the “Maputo Declaration on Agriculture and Food Security in Africa” (Oxfam, 2019). The Declaration contained several important decisions regarding agriculture capable of ensuring food security, but prominent among them was the “commitment for allocation of at least 10 percent of national budgetary resources to agriculture (Samuel, 2020). This was a five year’s development policy initiative for rural communities to boost agricultural development. The same vein, ratio of Nigeria's budget for agriculture to annual budget has been factored out to see if it falls short or not of the prescribed standard set by the Maputo Declaration on Agriculture and Food Security (Taiwo, 2022). Table 1.1 shows Nigeria’s annual budget with allocation in agricultural sector.

TABLE 1.1 NIGERIA’S ANNUAL BUDGET WITH ALLOCATION IN AGRICULTURAL SECTOR.

Year	Total Budget (N’ Billion/Trillion) (a)	Agriculture Allocation (N’ Billion) (b)	As % of Total budget $b/a*100$	As 10% of Total (N’ Billion) (d)	Variance from 10% Benchmark (N’ Billion)
2014	4,695,190,000,000	66,644,675,939	1.41	469,519,000,000	402,874,324,061
2015	4,493,363,957,158	40,659,020,717	0.90	449,336,395,716	408,677,374,999
2016	6,060,677,358,227	75,806,548,275	1.25	606,067,735,823	530,261,187,548
2017	7,441,175,486,758	135,545,345,061	1.82	744,117,548,675	608,572,203,614
2018	9,120,334,988,225	203,010,092,743	1.89	912,033,498,822.5	709,023,406,079.5
2019	8,916,964,099,373	107,218,344,102	1.20	891,696,409,937.3	784,478,065,835.3
2020	10.33	83	0.80	1.033 trillion	1.025 trillion
2021	13.588	110	0.81	1.3588 trillion	1.2488 trillion
2022	16.39	98,	0.58	1.639 trillion	1.541 trillion
				Gap	7.2548 trillion

Through Maputo agreement was a declaration, the African Union (AU) agreed to allocate at least 10% of its member countries' annual national budget to agriculture. Public resource allocation to agriculture in Nigeria is very low when judged against the most widely cited international benchmark (Oxfam, 2019). While some African countries such as Ghana, Uganda and Malawi have stabilized their budget expenditures on agriculture at around 10% of the total, Nigeria has consistently spent less than 5% of its annual budget on agriculture. Such a funding pattern clearly does not benefit the sector that is acknowledged to be a prime driver of growth and poverty reduction in the country as displayed in Table 1.0 for period of time.

A review of the budgetary allocation between 2014 and 2022 reveal the commitment of FGN to the sector. If the 10% Maputo Declaration benchmark been implemented, the national agriculture and food indices would probably have been better. From the Table 1.0 the state of allocations, agriculture sector is short of N3.65 trillion; an amount that is about 6 times the investment in the sector over the past 8 years which translates to N628.88 billion. Federal expenditure on agriculture decreased from 66 billion Naira in 2014, to 40 billion Naira in 2015 just a span of single year. At the same time, total federal expenditure increased from 4.2 trillion naira in to 5.2 trillion naira over the same period, implying a reduction in the share of agriculture in total federal expenditure. Also the total budget has risen from 4.695 trillion to 16.39 trillion, from 2014 to 2022, taking that into percentage, 349 % increase, calculating same percentage on agricultural allocation while ignoring 10% allocation, agriculture should received an allocation of 232.49 billion in 2022 but on the contrary it received only 98 billion giving a depecite of 134.49 billion. This is a worrying situation even though the impact of inflation has not been factored in (Oxfam, 2019). When this is done, agriculture expenditure would have reduced in both real and nominal terms (Oxfam, 2019). This means that Nigeria is performing poorer in terms of meeting the Maputo declaration of committing 10 percent budgetary resources to agriculture (Oxfam, 2019). Much more effort is needed to resuscitate this sector.. If this declaration is to be implemented, in 2022 agricultural sector should have been allocated 1.639 trillion, but got only 98 billion. For the span of the eight years Nigeria has lost 7.254 trillion naira in its allocation to the agricultural sector in accordance with Maputo declaration of committing 10 percent budgetary resources to agriculture.

As a result of the foregoing, almost all the National Agricultural Research Systems (NARS) have been under-budget, and cannot perform its stated objectives. National policies especially as macroeconomic reforms cannot therefore be implemented by these agencies. Nearly all the agricultural research institutes are owned and managed by the federal government; the State and Local governments, which bare closer to the rural farmers, have no much research institutes, and in states, there research departments are under the agricultural development programmes (ADP), they are barely functional and mostly underfunded. This means that all decisions on the funding, direction and implementation of research activities are taken from the federal capital. The consequence of this is not only an over-centralization of agricultural administration, but also that those involved are hardly in touch with the realities on ground (Oxfam, 2019). This results into a much greater range in development of new technologies, while the available ones are not available to common farmer for improve production systems.

2.7 WEAK INFRASTRUCTURE AND INCONSISTENCY OF POLICIES

Weak infrastructures, inconsistency in government policies and lack of sustainability have always been major challenges in the development of agriculture in Nigeria. Some of the problems that could result from inconsistent agricultural policies in Nigeria include: high level of apathy on the part of the farmers regarding any policies or interventions from the government side because nobody knows time span of such; dynamism in initiated policies characterized by frequent changes and restrictions, thus leading to uncertainty in production-supply chain; and failure in the adopted agricultural system for farming and processing (Oxfam, 2019). The economic recovery and restructuring policy being stage for implementation by the Federal government is limited to some macroeconomic stability, with farmers continue to face unfavorable terms to agricultural policies that may have been stagnant or passing through undue delay in chain line from farm inputs implements such as improved seed and agro chemicals to processing and supply, with lower and more uncertain prices.

The implementing agencies for agricultural policies in Nigeria lack potential sustainability, for example the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (through the National Programme on Food Security (NPFS)) and the Bank of Industry (BOI) Limited have made a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) designated BOI as the Fund Custodian and Administrator with the responsibility of fund disbursement, implementing and monitoring the projects as well as recovering

the loan and interest there from in promoting national food security. BOI has a target on Agro-allied processors and farmers to enhance the productivity of the Apex Farmers Association (AFA), registered co-operative groups and SMEs in all thirty-six (36) States but not to mention, now how many of the beneficiaries of these loans can be presented that sustained the target goal of the said policy leading to improve agricultural practices in their localities, how many are still enjoying the programme, these are serious question that requires answers. If policy is designed to a target goal, it has to be monitored and implemented such that the said goals are achieved. Seen this as a laudable policy, but where are the achieved goals?

2.8 AGRICULTURAL CREDIT

Agricultural credit facilities have to be available to sustain or boast the zeal of the farming population aimed at improving the access to credit facilities. So many where available, but to mention few:

2.8.1 AGRICULTURAL CREDIT SUPPORT SCHEME (ACSS)

According to Today Magazine, ACSS is an initiative of the Federal Government and the Central Bank of Nigeria with the active support and participation of the Bankers Committee created in June 2019. The Scheme has a prescribed fund of N 50.0 billion. Radius times also reported that ACSS was introduced to enable farmers benefit from untapped agricultural potentials in Nigeria, reduce inflation, lower the cost of agricultural production (i. e. food items), generate surplus for export, increase Nigeria's foreign earnings as well as diversify its revenue base. This project operate at national level through Central Implementation Committee (CIC) (Radius Times) while at the State levels, the Scheme can operates through State Implementation Committees (SICs) instituted by the states to ensure that the objectives of the scheme is realized without any hindrance (Start Credits). To Start Credits, access loans under ACSS, farmers and agro-allied entrepreneurs can secure loans through their respective state chapters, farmers associations and State Implementation Committees. The funds are designed to farmers and agro-allied entrepreneurs at a single-digit interest rate of 8.0 percent. At the commencement of the project support, banks will grant loans to qualified applicants at 14.0 per cent interest rate which is higher than that specified by CBN, it is a clear sign on poor policy implementation. But not sure that the programme is still running and buttress the point clearer one cannot confirm the benefitting figures and the profit generated by those in the said programme. These are part of the programmes that lack continuity and poor management strategy, the policy initiator has to have a clear record of all these programmes to see its success or failure in its implementation. But here we have only media broadcast and startup of such, subsequently no follow up.

2.8.2 COMMERCIAL AGRICULTURE CREDIT SCHEME (CACS)

From the official website of Central Bank of Nigeria (2009), CACS was established in join collaboration between Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources (FMA&WR) to allow access for farmers into commercial credit scheme to provide finance for the country's agricultural value chain (production, processing, storage and marketing) (ThisdayLive, 2022). These will in turn increased agricultural production to moderate inflationary pressures and assist the Banks to achieve its goal of price stability in the country. The primary objectives of the Scheme published by ThisdayLive are to:

- Fast-track development of agricultural sector by providing credit facilities to large-scale commercial farmers at a single digit interest rate;
- Enhance national food security by increasing food supply, limiting effects of lower agricultural produce and products prices, hence promoting low food inflation rate;
- Reduce credit cost in agricultural production to enable farmers have appreciable profit,
- And to finally increase output, generate employment, diversify revenue base, sustain level of foreign exchange, provide input for manufacturing on a sustainable basis.

The Scheme is a subcomponent of the Federal Government of Nigerias Commercial Agriculture Development Programme (CADP) is financed through a N200billion Bond raised by the Debt Management Office (DMO). Loans aimed at 9 percent maximum interest rate. As far from inception, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) is yet to declare or account for the beneficiaries of the said policy neither it authenticate the success of the Scheme over the period of the time by the farmers who access the loans. The project is expected to jointly ensure that the scheme is implemented successfully (Impact

Assessment). But till date no report was made available to such in regard to day-to-day implementation of the Scheme undertaken by a Technical Implementation Committee (TIC) which is made up of Director of Development Finance Department, CBN as the Chairman, Head of Agricultural Credit Support Division, CBN and Consulting Group as members. CACS in their home page said, it operate in two tranches of N100billion each, the 1st Phase of the tranche ran from May to December, 2009, while the 2nd tranche commenced in February, 2010 CACS (2022).

2.8.3 NIRSAL

The Nigeria Incentive-Based Risk Sharing System for Agricultural Lending (NIRSAL Plc.) is a \$500million Non-Bank Financial Institution wholly-owned by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) created to Redefine, Dimension, Measure, Re-Price and Share agribusiness-related credit risks in Nigeria. It was established jointly in collaboration between Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD) and Nigerian Bankers' Committee in 2013, NIRSAL's mandate is to stimulate flow of finance and investments into agricultural sector by de-risking agriculture & agribusiness finance in the value chain, fixing agricultural value chains, building long-term capacity, and institutionalizing incentives for agricultural lending through its five (5) strategic pillars, namely: Risk Sharing, Insurance, Technical Assistance, Incentives and Rating obtained from NIRSAL website.

The programme is an instrumental to protect financiers and investors from possible losses in a finance/credit transaction through a risk sharing arrangement under which NIRSAL indemnifies the lender or investor principal and accrued interest for limited of a pre-agreed CRG rate. They are to offer serves as at comfort to financiers and investors, encouraging them to lend to the agribusiness against losses over the life of the underlying credit contract between a financier and actors in the agricultural value chain. It covers credit of term loans, and/or debt instruments such as short, medium, and long-term, loan excluding overdrafts. It is purchased at 1% (upfront payment) of the loan value and subsequent outstanding balances of the loan annually. The Scheme is designed to reward diligent borrower behavior through discretionary rebates of up to 40% of interest paid on NIRSAL CRG-backed agribusiness loans, thereby reducing the effective interest rate for borrowers with a good credit history. It also rebate payments apply only to pre-approved transactions made every 90 days subject to compliance with the loan's underlying conditions and timely repayments of during the review period. With these programme many farmers can borrow huge money looking at it simplified interest and credit scheme (NIRSAL home page). However, majorly, the loan was not used in agricultural activities as many sees these as free money from federal government. The initiator has to ensure that the loans collected are purely utilized in agricultural activities. Also the trace of the success to this policy cannot be authenticated, so also its significance in achieving the said target.

2.8.4 ANCHOR BORROWERS PROGRAMME

According to Premium Times Nigeria (May 21, 2021), Anchor Borrowers Programme which target Over 3.1 million farmers financed — based on CBN estimates. N300 billion had been air-marked and disbursed to companies operating in the southern part of Nigeria. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) urged farmers to repay their loans in order to sustain the Programme. According to premiumtime, the Anchor Borrowers' Programme was aimed at every farmer eligible to get a solar home system that will provide electricity to power their essential home appliances. The aim was to develop a repayment framework that will allow farmers to use their farm produce as repayment for the electricity consumed by the beneficiaries of the scheme. The incentive is aimed at improving the standard of living of farmers in rural communities in Nigeria. Since inception of the Programme a total of 3,107,890 farmers had been financed for the cultivation of 3,801,397 hectares across 21 commodities through 23 Participating Financial Institutions in the 36 States of the Federation and FCT, CBN-RIFAN partnership also financed 221,450 farmers for the cultivation of 221,450 hectares in 32 States. As part of efforts to boost food production locally, the planned was to cultivate a minimum of one million hectares of rice through partnership with farmers of Rice Farmers Association of Nigeria (RIFAN) and prime or private anchors for each planting season in 2021. While also unveiling aggressive production plans for maize, wheat, soyabeans, cassava, sorghum and cassava, rice millers also gaining momentum as the programme intends to finance millers to grow their own paddy during wet season. To this day, the statistics of the benefiting farmers is available, but however, its significance to improve in food production chain, food security, local farming and etc is yet to be evaluated. We need policies that their value chain can have impact on the real economy as well supporting the farmer to improve his output in augmenting food security challenge.

3. WAY FORWARD

There are some approaches are possible for achieving sustainability of food security, these include:

- i. Limiting food losses and waste,
- ii. Eating more plant-based foods,
- iii. Increasing budgetary allocation to agricultural sector for improvement on food production to ensure sufficient food supply.
- iv. Reducing climate and global warming,
- v. Controlled global population growth,
- vi. Adaptation of strategies and policy responses to global food supply chain,
- vii. Change agricultural practices,
- viii. Proper handling water rain water for small scale irrigation,
- ix. Proper land use management strategies,
- x. Postharvest food processing,
- xi. Food prices and safety management strategies.
- xii. etc

4. CONCLUSION

These are some few policies to mention out of the numerous programmes and polices initiated by Nigerian government towards agricultural improvement in local and home grown food items to ensure food security. However, the challenge is proper implementation and sustainability of these programmes. Majority of the programmes cease to exist and some are no more. The bedeviling issue is to ensure all the initiated programme have reached its targeted goal and was sustained until the target time is reach. Subsequently a follow up should be executed to assess the level of it success, good tracked record should be implemented. The government needs to look at the Maputo declaration of committing 10 percent budgetary resources to agriculture ensuring its sustainability then we can dream of sustainable food security.

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